

Assessing Situation Awareness while Driving with Automation

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Abstract: In a driving simulator study, different levels of situation awareness (SA) were created experimentally and the suitability of different methods for assessing SA and their relation to each other were investigated. N=41 participants experienced driving with an automated driving function (AD) in four conditions (SAE level 2 vs. two versions of SAE level 3 vs. SAE level 3 with black scenery during AD mode) which were expected to result in different levels of SA. Results from the post-drive questionnaire indicate that while being in AD mode, three levels of SA could be induced for aspects of SA perceived via visual perception of the road. For other aspects of SA and perception during takeover request, results show reduced variation of SA between conditions with only two levels remaining. These two levels are also in-line with reaction times in takeover situations. In summary, we could induce different levels of SA and the used post-drive questionnaire was suited to measure those differences.

1. Introduction

Situation awareness (SA) was first investigated in aviation and is defined as “the perception of the elements in the environment within a volume of time and space, the comprehension of their meaning and the projection of their status in the near future” (Endsley, 1988, p. 97). The driver is required to maintain SA all the time while driving with level 2 AD (L2-AD; SAE, 2021) although SA might be compromised by vigilance decrements. Conversely, with level 3 AD (L3-AD; SAE, 2021) the driver is allowed to lose SA in automated mode and then needs to regain it only at takeover requests (TOR).

To measure SA, interview or questionnaire methods like SART (Taylor, 2017) are used as well as eye tracking (Moore & Gugerty, 2010; van de Merwe, van Dijk, & Zon, 2012), physiological measures (Zhang et al., 2020) or probe measures. In probe measures which are similar to SAGAT (Endsley, 1995), knowledge on the situation is asked from the subject directly in or after the situation (Strybel et al., 2016). In AD, SA is mainly investigated by means of eye tracking measures, i.e. visual attention (Liang et al., 2021), by the response to critical events (Gold et al., 2013; Merat & Jamson, 2009) and also by probe measures (e.g., Sirkin, Martelaro, Johns, & Ju, 2017).

For driving with AD, it proved difficult to show a relation between different measures of SA like SAGAT, questionnaires or takeover performance (e.g. van den Beukel, van der Voort & Eger, 2016; Cortens, 2019; Schwindt et al. 2023). However, for future research on SA in AD, it needs to be understood, which of the methods used in the literature are capable of measuring SA in AD and how the different methods relate to each other.

2. Method

2.1 Experimental approach

A driving simulator study was conducted with the aim to create different level of SA while driving with AD. Four conditions were implemented.

- L2: drivers are instructed to stay attentive and monitor the automation all the time.
- L3: drivers are allowed to be inattentive during the automated drive. They watch a video while being in automated mode.
- L3+: same as the L3 condition but with an extended HMI-version which provides more information in case of a TOR.
- Black: same as the L3 condition but in automated mode the visual input to the driver is reduced by not showing the driving environment. During AD mode, the projected scenery is turned black. The scenery becomes visible at the beginning of a TOR and remains visible during manual driving.

Every driver participated in two experimental sessions of about 3 hours each and experienced all four conditions in randomized order.

The study took place in the high-fidelity moving base driving simulator of the WIVW GmbH. The simulation software was SILAB® Version 6.0 (WIVW GmbH, Veitshöchheim). In the study, participants drove with a simulated L2/L3 motorway AD which could automatically adjust speed and distance, stay in its lane and overtake slower vehicles. In case of a system boundary, control was given back after an acoustical and visual TOR with a total takeover time of 10 seconds. At a TOR drivers had to deactivate the AD by button press and continue driving manually.

The AD was experienced during drives of 50 minutes, in which sections with stable driving in AD alternated with situations with system boundaries. Per drive, between 7 and 8 TORs occurred in situations with mostly medium demands to the driver like construction sites or highway intersections.

2.1 Data collection

Data collection consisted of a variety of different measures for assessing SA:

- a post-drive questionnaire assessing the perception of different aspects of the driving situation while being in automated mode and at TORs using a 5-point Likert-scale

- experienced situational criticality directly after each TOR on a 10-point scale (based on Neukum et al. (2008), range: 1=harmless, 10=uncontrollable)
- logging of vehicle and AD state to calculate metrics like takeover reaction times to TORs.

2.2 Sample

The study was conducted with N=41 (20 female, 21 male) participants. On average they were 45 years of age (sd=16.3).

2.3 Analyses

In the following, the focus is on the analysis of subjective data. Takeover performance is assessed by analysing the reaction time until the AD system is deactivated. For measures collected per takeover situation, indicators are first average per driver and condition and are then analysed.

3. Results

3.1 Post-drive evaluation

In the post-drive evaluation (see figure 1a), there were significant effects of condition (see table 1) on items asking for situational knowledge while driving in automated mode. For items focusing on the visual perception of relevant aspects of the driving scenery (lane, other vehicles etc.) the highest ratings were given in the L2, the lowest in the black condition with the two L3 conditions laying in between. For items relating to aspects that can be perceived outside the forward view (speed on speedometer, vehicle dynamics, sounds) the difference lies between L2 and the other three conditions.

Table 1 Results of ANOVAs on impact of condition on subjective evaluation.

Item	df	F	p
knew in which lane	3,111	32.6	<.001
knew car in front	3,111	52.3	<.001
knew my speed	3,111	18.9	<.001
focused on driving	3,111	47.8	<.001
observed environment	3,111	64.6	<.001
were aware of sounds	3,111	7.9	<.001
knew car on next lane	3,111	68.7	<.001
focused on other things	3,111	35.5	<.001
felt vehicle dynamics	3,111	4.2	<.01
knew why TOR	3,111	8.5	<.001
knew on which lane	3,111	7.4	<.001
knew vehicles around me	3,111	8.4	<.001
knew how to take control back	3,111	3.4	<.05

Figure 1. Post-drive ratings on situational knowledge and attention (a) while being in AD mode (b) during TORs.

If it comes to assessing the driving situation at the time of a TOR (figure 1b), participants highly agreed in all conditions that they knew quickly important aspects of the situation and what to do. Again, there was a significant impact of condition (see table 1). Subjects reported a significantly quicker perception of the situation in the L2 compared to the black condition for all items, with L3 and L3+ lying in between.

Average experienced situational criticality of takeover situations is in the range of harmless and varies between 1.6 for L2 and 2.4 for the black condition (see figure 2). There is a significant difference with TORs being experienced as less critical in L2 compared to black condition, with L3 and L3+ lying in between ($F(3,117)=3.5, p<.05$).

Takeover reaction time differs between conditions ($F(3, 117)=8.8, p<.001$) with L2 having an average reaction time of 2.1 seconds and the other three conditions ranging between 2.5 and 2.7 seconds (figure 2).

Figure 2 Experienced criticality (a) and reaction time until AD is turned off after a TOR (b).

4. Discussion

Items from the post-drive questionnaire addressing the perception of the driving scene during AD mode show the intended variation of SA with L2 with the highest level, the black condition with the lowest level and L3 and L3+ lying in between. Similarly, in the evaluation of the takeover situations directly after each TOR, the conditions group into three levels with L2 being the least and black the most critical.

However, for items of the post-drive questionnaire that relate to situational aspects perceivable outside the forward view and to perception at a TOR, the differences between conditions are reduced. Now, mainly L2 corresponds to a higher level of SA while the three other conditions become very similar. A similar pattern with a difference between L2 and the three other conditions is found for takeover responses measured by takeover times.

The reported takeover time is a commonly used measure for assessing driver performance at TORs (Yining Cao, Zhou et al., 2021) that reflects the timely component of a takeover response. Still, to fully understand the relation between SA and takeover reaction, indicators are needed (like TOC-rating, Naujoks, Wiedemann, Schömig, Jarosch, & Gold, 2018) that go beyond the reported timely aspect of takeover performance.

One explanation for the two different patterns of differences between conditions could be that during AD mode there were indeed three different levels of SA. In takeover situations, drivers were able to compensate the reduced SA in the black condition so that this condition did no longer differ from the L3 and the L3+ condition. However, the additional effort required during the takeover response is still reflected in the experienced overall criticality of the situation.

5. Conclusions

The used post-drive questionnaire was suited to reflect differences in SA. This is especially true for items assessing SA while being in AD mode. Here, results indicate that even the perception of aspects of the environment that do not directly result from enhanced visual attention (like vehicle dynamics, noise) might be positively impacted in L2 compared to L3.

For a final understanding of the relation between the different measures of SA at different points in time (during AD mode, at TOR), the data needs to be analysed in more detail. More indicators like gaze patterns, situational aspects of the takeover situations or a more fine-grained analysis of takeover response will give more detailed insight into the different levels of SA and how they impact drivers' response to TORs.

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References

- Cortens, B. (2019). *Impact of Alert Design and Hazard Direction on Driver Behaviour and Understanding in a Simulated Autonomous Vehicle* (Master' thesis, University of Guelph, Guelph, Kanada). Retrieved from <https://atrium.lib.uoguelph.ca/xmlui/handle/10214/15935>
- Endsley, M. R. (1988). Design and evaluation for situation awareness enhancement. Paper presented at the *Proceedings of the Human Factors Society annual meeting*
- Endsley, M. R. (1995). Measurement of situation awareness in dynamic systems. *Human Factors*, 37(1), 65-84.
- Gold, C., Damböck, D., Lorenz, L., & Bengler, K. (2013). "Take over!" How long does it take to get the driver back into the loop? Paper presented at the *Human Factors and Ergonomics Society 57th Annual Meeting*, San Diego, CA, USA.
- Liang, N., Yang, J., Yu, D., Prakah-Asante, K. O., Curry, R., Blommer, M., . . . Pitts, B. J. (2021). Using eye-tracking to investigate the effects of pre-takeover visual engagement on situation awareness during automated driving. *Accident Analysis & Prevention*, 157, 106143.
- Merat, N., & Jamson, A. H. (2009). Is Drivers' Situation Awareness Influenced by a Fully Automated Driving Scenario? Paper presented at the *Human factors, security and safety*.
- Moore, K., & Gugerty, L. (2010). Development of a novel measure of situation awareness. The case of eye movement analysis. Paper presented at the *Human Factors and Ergonomics Society Annual Meeting*

- Naujoks, F., Wiedemann, K., Schömig, N., Jarosch, O., & Gold, C. (2018). Expert-based controllability assessment of control transitions from automated to manual driving. *MethodsX* 5: 579-592.
- Neukum, A., Lübbecke, T., Krüger, H.-P., Mayser, C. & Steinle, J. (2008). ACC-Stop&Go: Fahrerverhalten an funktionalen Systemgrenzen. In M. Maurer & C. Stiller (Eds.), *5. Workshop Fahrerassistenzsysteme - FAS 2008*. pp. 141-150. Karlsruhe: fmrt.
- SAE. (2021). J3016: Taxonomy and Definitions for Terms Related to Driving Automation Systems for On-Road Motor Vehicles (Vol. J3016), SAE International/ISO, www.sae.org
- Schwindt, S., von Graevenitz, P., & Abendroth, B. (2023). Situational Awareness in the Context of Automated Driving - Adapting the Situational Awareness Global Assessment Technique. *Human Factors in Transportation*, Vol. 95, 2023, 161–171, <https://doi.org/10.54941/ahfe1003802>
- Sirkin, D., Martelaro, N., Johns, M., & Ju, W. (2017). Toward measurement of situation awareness in autonomous vehicles. Paper presented at the *2017 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*.
- Strybel, T. Z., Chiappe, D., Vu, K.-P. L., Miramontes, A., Battiste, H., & Battiste, V. (2016). A comparison of methods for assessing situation awareness in current day and future air traffic management operations: Graphics-based vs text-based online probe systems. *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, 49(19), 31-35.
- Taylor, R. M. (2017). Situational awareness rating technique (SART): The development of a tool for aircrew systems design. In *Situational awareness* (pp. 111-128): Routledge.
- van den Beukel, A. P., van der Voort, M. C., & Eger, A. O. (2016). Supporting the changing driver's task: Exploration of interface designs for supervision and intervention in automated driving. *Transportation research part F: Traffic psychology and behaviour*, 43, 279-301. doi:10.1016/j.trf.2016.09.009
- van de Merwe, K., van Dijk, H., & Zon, R. (2012). Eye movement as an indicator of situation awareness in a flight simulator experiment. *The International Journal of Aviation Psychology*, 22(1). doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/10508414.2012.635129>
- Yining Cao, Y., Zhou, F., Molnar, L., Robert, L.P., Tilbury, D.M. & Yang, X. J. Towards Standardized Metrics for Measuring Takeover Performance in Conditionally Automated Driving: A Literature Review, *Proceedings of the 65st Annual Meeting of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society*, Oct. 4 - 7, 2021 at the Baltimore, MD.
- Zhang, T., Yang, J., Liang, N., Pitts, B. J., Prakah-Asante, K. O., Curry, R., . . . Yu, D. (2020). Physiological measurements of situation awareness: a systematic review. *Human Factors*.